

EXPLORING PARENTAL INVOLVEMENT AND SEX EDUCATION IN PREVENTING ADOLESCENT RISK BEHAVIORS

Carmelita M. Lamberte, Clarissa Q. Pulido, Maricel L. Garcia, Roden A. Samson

College of Arts and Sciences, Pamantasan ng Lungsod ng Muntinlupa, Muntinlupa City, Philippines

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17638193>

ABSTRACT

The study established the significance of the relationship between parental involvement among parents of adolescent students and the teaching of sex education towards preventing adolescent risk behaviors, during the first semester of the Academic Year 2023-2024. A mixed method of research design, the Triangulation and Quantitative Correlational methods were utilized in order to respond systematically and objectively to the problems posed in this study. A total of 45 parents, selected through purposive sampling, took part in this study. Data were collected using researcher-made questionnaires: the Parental Involvement Questionnaire (PIQ), the Teaching of Sex Education Questionnaire (TSEQ), and the Risk Behavior Questionnaire (RBQ). Results of the study revealed that parental involvement and the teaching of sex education among adolescents have a significant influence on the adolescent risk behaviors of their children. Further, these results disclose that parents should consistently act as good examples to their children and always provide direct communication, constantly remind their children of the religious beliefs that they have, and family customs should be maintained. Likewise, sex education is very important to be taught formally in school and informally at home.

Keywords: *Parental Involvement, Sex Education, Adolescent Risk Behaviors*

INTRODUCTION

Adolescents experience rapid physical, cognitive, and psychosocial growth that affects how they feel, think, make decisions, and interact with the world around them. During this phase, adolescents establish patterns of behavior – for instance, related to diet, physical activity, substance use, sexual activity, and early pregnancy that can protect their health and the health of others around them, or put their health at risk now and in the future.

As cited by the World Health Organization (2019), adolescents need information, including age-appropriate comprehensive sexuality education; opportunities to develop life skills; health services that are acceptable, equitable, appropriate, and effective; and safe and supportive environments in order for them to grow and develop holistically.

On one hand, tobacco use, pregnancy, drug and alcohol abuse, and gang violence among adolescents continue to be found in surprisingly younger teenagers, even though considerable amounts of money and effort have been expended to provide appropriate information relating to the consequences of these activities. These risk behaviors and the related outcomes cause a consequential drain on medical resources, the social welfare system, the courts, and the quality of life for society in general.

On the other hand, parental involvement is multifaceted in nature because it subsumes a wide variety of parental behavioral patterns and parenting practices. It has been described as: representing many different parental behaviors; parenting practices such as parental aspirations for their child's academic achievement; parental communication with their children about school; parental participation in school activities; parental communications with teachers about their child; and parental rules at home, which are considered to be education-related.

Regarding sex education, the Responsible Parenthood and Reproductive Health Act of 2012 was passed, integrating sexuality education into the existing curriculum for learners from kindergarten to Grade 12; however, it has yet to be fully implemented. In 2018, the Department of Education established the Policy Guidelines on the Implementation of Comprehensive Sexuality Education (CSE) in an effort to reduce the increasing prevalence of teen pregnancy, sexual assault, and STIs such as HIV, among young Filipinos. Likewise, it aims to effectively address the needs of the learners for health and protection through education and is designed to ensure that the learners are receiving comprehensive and appropriate information that can advance gender equality and empowerment, decrease the risks of having unsafe sex, and increase responsible family planning.

Moreover, the study was conducted at one of the adopted communities of the university since 2017 up to the present, a small community located in Brgy. Poblacion, Muntinlupa City. As an adopted community, the university is committed to assisting and supervising the probable needs, issues, and problems that could affect the well-being of the members and the future of the community. Part of doing these is to realize the heart

of the university's vision-mission of empowering people and developing productive and God-loving individuals in society. However, significant actions to address such concerns should be data-driven and research-based.

At this juncture, the researchers, who are faculty members of the said university, specifically, from the College of Arts and Sciences, decided to embark on conducting this study about exploring parental involvement and sex education in preventing adolescent risk behaviors, as they believe that adolescent risk behaviors are part of the social phenomenon problems today, which need to be addressed closely. Likewise, they aimed to contribute to attaining the college vision, which is to be a Center of Development where faculty thrive in producing relevant and outstanding research for the welfare of the local community.

Research Questions

This study explored the influence of parental involvement in giving guidance and sex education to their adolescent children towards preventing risk behaviors. It aimed to determine whether the expected behavior has been clearly delineated by the parents to their children in precise directives. Considering the limited ability of this age group for abstract thinking, this study aimed to prove the influence of parents during adolescence, and how parental involvement and sex education have a measurable impact on the behavior of the adolescent.

Accordingly, it aimed to seek answers to the following research questions:

1. How does parental involvement of respondents describe in the form of:
 - 1.1 Good example,
 - 1.2 Family customs,
 - 1.3 Direct communication, and
 - 1.4 Religious belief?
2. What is the perception of the parent-respondents on the teaching of sex education in the context of:
 - 2.1 Formally taught in school; and
 - 2.2 Informally taught at home?
3. What are the frequent risk behaviors that the adolescents are involved with:
 - 3.1 Alcohol use;
 - 3.2 Illegal drug use;
 - 3.3 Gambling;
 - 3.4 Sexual activity;
 - 3.5 Smoking cigarettes; and
 - 3.6 Socializing with problematic peers?
4. How significant is the association between parental involvement, teaching sex education, and adolescent risk behaviors?
5. Based on the findings of the study, what Intervention Program may be proposed?

Hypotheses of the Study

At a 95% level of significance, the null hypotheses of the study were tested using a standard statistical formula.

Ho1: There is no significant relationship between parental involvement and adolescent-risk behaviors.

Ho2: The teaching of sex education is not significantly associated with adolescent-risk behaviors.

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

This enquiry utilized a mixed-method research design, the Triangulation and Quantitative Correlational methods, which explore multiple datasets that can help enhance the validity and credibility of findings, as well as the relationship between two variables using effect statistics. It used a researcher-made questionnaire, which was administered through an actual survey to the target respondents. A purposive sampling technique was used in selecting the actual respondents of the study. Descriptive and inferential statistics were applied in treating all the generated quantitative data.

Moreover, qualitative data were gathered through actual interviews using open-ended questionnaires.

The Respondents of the Study

The investigation involved a purposive sample of 45 parents from the adopted community in Poblacion, Muntinlupa City, which is the research locale of the study. The small community has an estimated population of 200 families only. The parents have at least one Senior High student who is currently enrolled at different Senior High schools within the City. These students normally range from 16 to 19 years of age. They will be selected because early adolescent cognitive development is generally characterized as the transition between linear and abstract thinking. For this age group, standards and expectations of behavior must be clearly defined in direct, concrete terms to have the desired impact. The time reference of the study is the 1st Semester of Academic Year 2023-2024.

On the other hand, the parents in this study refer to all the people who are involved in the child's education, which may include the biological parents, adoptive parents, grandparents, aunts, uncles, step-parents, and guardians who carry the primary responsibility for the child's education and development (CPTA, 2003).

Instrument

For the purpose of eliciting vivid information that could support the objectives of the study and to find out the preeminent results in evaluating the frequently engaged risk behaviors of the adolescent children of the parent-respondents, as well as their parental involvement in providing guidance and sex education, the needed data were drawn from the primary sources, of which empirical data were obtained through the use of self-constructed questionnaires.

This questionnaire was intended for the selected parents which comprised two (2) parts: (1) Part 1 encompasses the level of parental involvement of the parent-respondents in preventing adolescent risk behaviors and their perception on the teaching of sex education whether this would be formally taught in school or informally taught at home; and (2) Part 2 cites the adolescent risk behaviors that the adolescent-children are frequently involved with as perceived by the parent-respondents. Relative to this concept, the researchers also considered the perceptions and experiences of the respondents, of which data were gathered during the in-depth interviews, actual observations, and one-on-one discussions. The validity and reliability of the Parental Involvement Questionnaire (PIQ), the Teaching of Sex Education Questionnaire (TSEQ), and the Risk Behavior Questionnaire (RBQ) were established using specific psychometric methods. These instruments were rigorously pre-tested and validated, referencing established research and utilizing standard statistical software, specifically SPSS, to ensure they accurately and consistently measured parental involvement, sex education practices, and adolescent risk behaviors within the study's context.

Data Analysis/ Statistical Treatment

For in-depth analysis, the gathered aggregate raw data from this research were studied, measured, analyzed, and interpreted to find the relationship or influence of parental involvement and sex education towards preventing adolescent risk behaviors. Hence, the researchers utilized both descriptive and inferential statistics to resolve the problems of the study.

In Descriptive statistics, the ordinal data gathered were calculated, and the weighted mean of central tendency measures was used for the portions of the questionnaires with options of assigned points.

In Inferential Statistics, the analysis of a significant relationship between the respondents' level of parental involvement and adolescents' risk behaviors was determined through the application of the Pearson r Correlation Coefficient and t-test. The former statistical tool was used to describe the relationship between two variables or how the variations of y go with x . It gives information on the Amount and Direction, while the latter was used to test the significance of the relationships, either significant or not a significant correlate or if it is significantly non-zero as a null hypothesis in the form:

$H_0: P = 0$ against a non-directional alternative hypothesis in the form $H_a: P \neq 0$.

RESULTS

Table 1: Summary of Values of the Respondents' Assessment on Parental Involvement

Parental Involvement	Average Weighted Mean	Verbal Interp.	Rank
1. Good example	3.63	O	1
2. Family customs	2.57	So	3
3. Direct communication	2.32	S	4
4. Religious belief	3.54	O	2
General Average Weighted Mean	3.02	So	
<i>Legend:</i> 4.50 -5.00= Always (A) 2.50 – 3.49= Sometimes (So) 3.50 -4.49= Often (O) 1.50 – 2.49= Seldom (S) 1.00-1.49= Never (N)			

Table 2: Summary of Values of the Respondents' Assessment on the Teaching of Sex Education

Sex Education	Average Weighted Mean	Verbal Interp.
1. Formally taught in school	4.65	SA
2. Informally taught at home	2.39	D
General Average Weighted Mean	3.52	A
<i>Legend:</i> 4.50 – 5.00 = Strongly Agree (SA) 2.50 – 3.49 = Uncertain (U) 1.00 – 1.49 = Strongly Disagree (SD) 3.50 – 4.49 = Agree (A) 1.50 – 2.49 = Disagree (D)		

Table 3: Summary Values of Parents' Assessment on the Adolescents' Frequent Risk Behaviors

Adolescent Risk Behaviors	Average Weighted Mean	Verbal Interp.	Rank
1. Alcohol use	3.79	O	2
2. Illegal drug use	1.63	S	6
3. Gambling	3.42	So	3
4. Sexual activity	2.78	So	5
5. Smoking cigarettes	4.16	O	1
6. Socializing with problematic peers	3.24	So	4
General Average Weighted Mean	3.17	So	
<i>Legend:</i> 4.50 -5.00= Always (A) 2.50 – 3.49= Sometimes (So) 3.50 -4.49= Often (O) 1.50 – 2.49= Seldom (S) 1.00-1.49= Never (N)			

Table 4: Relationship Between Parental Involvement (x1) Adolescent-Risk Behaviors (y)

Independent (x)	Dependent (y) Adolescent Risk Behavior				
	Pearson Correlation (r)	r ² %	Sig. (2-tailed) p-value	Interpretation	Decision
Parental Involvement (x1)	-0.407165*	0.165783	0.024763	p<.05	Reject Ho
Sex Education (x2)	-0.423061*	0.178981	0.046219	p<.05	Reject Ho
* Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed)					
<i>Decision Rule:</i> Reject Ho if p-value for slope ≤ (0.05)					

DISCUSSION

1. The Parental Involvement of the Respondents

The summary of the parent-respondents' assessments on their involvement as parents in guiding and instructing their adolescent children is shown in Table 1. This can take four forms: good example, family customs, direct communication, and religious belief.

Using the aggregated results of the assessments, the good example ranks first, as affirmed by the highest average weighted mean of 3.63. It is followed by religious belief, with an average weighted mean of 3.54. These two parental involvements are both rated as "Often" by the respondents. On the other hand, family customs rank third, which was rated as "Sometimes" by the respondents, while direct communication ranks fourth, which was rated as "Seldom." These are confirmed by the average weighted means of 2.57 and 2.32, respectively.

In this instance, the results affirm that among the four (4) parental involvements, the respondents of the study who are parents of the adolescent students, "often" show good examples to their children. This implies that regularly, they attend the school's parent-teacher conferences, frequently support their children's emotional and academic needs, and time and again motivate them to participate in the different school's extra-curricular activities. Oftentimes, they remind their children about their "religious belief" in God's existence, about the place for people after death (heaven and hell), and about praying and reading God's words.

Conversely, they "Sometimes" practiced family customs, which implies that they occasionally go for outings with their children, or have meals together, and at times inculcate good discipline in their children. On the other hand, they asserted to have "Seldom" direct communication with their children. In other words, they hardly ever initiate discussion about their children's studies and rarely allow them to explain their viewpoints.

Consistently, the general average weighted mean of 3.02 asserts that in totality, as parental involvement is concerned, the parents have interactions with their children's

development, academic success, and future endeavors at home and school, but only for “Sometimes”. Hence, they sporadically showed commitment and participation on the part of the school life and well-being of their children.

Furthermore, this result strongly supports the perspective outlined by Lyu et al. (2019), which cited that parental involvement includes direct and indirect interaction with children as well as pertains to parents’ control or support of their children, through various activities, including mentoring, monitoring, or facilitating the learning environment.

2. The Teaching of Sex Education

Table 2 summarizes the respondents’ assessments of the aspects of teaching sex education that may be taught formally in school or informally at home.

Based on the data shown in the table, it can be noted that the parent-respondents “Strongly Agree” on the importance of sex education as a subject matter that should be formally taught in the school. This is confirmed by the average weighted mean of 4.65. Hence, they believe that learning sex education in school helps in preventing sexually transmitted diseases and teenage pregnancies among the youth.

On the other hand, they disagree that sex education should be taught at home and left to the parents. This is affirmed by the average weighted mean of 2.39. This further implies that they feel comfortable as well as not responsible for discussing matters of sexuality, reproduction, and sexual health education with their children.

In a gist, the general average weighted mean of 3.52 affirms that the parent-respondents “Agree” on the notion that sex education should be formally taught in the school and not at home. In other words, they are certain that the teachers are more capable of teaching sex education to their children.

Moreover, this result strongly upholds on the Policy Guidelines of Department of Education (2018) in the Implementation of Comprehensive Sexuality Education (CSE) which aims to effectively address the needs of the learners for health and protection through education and is designed to ensure that the learners are receiving comprehensive and appropriate information that can reduce the increasing prevalence of teen pregnancy, sexual assault, and STIs such as HIV, among young Filipinos.

3. The Adolescents’ Frequent Risk Behaviors

Table 3 provides records of a summary of the parent-respondents’ ratings of the risk behaviors that their adolescent children are frequently engaged with.

Scrutinizing the average weighted means of the six (6) adolescent risk behaviors, these are variedly assessed by the respondents, falling into three categories: “Seldom,” “Sometimes,” and “Often”. These are established by the average weighted means ranging from 1.63 to 4.16.

However, using the aggregated results of the assessments, smoking cigarettes ranks first as confirmed by the highest average weighted mean of 4.16, followed by alcohol use with the average weighted mean of 3.79. These two (2) adolescent risk behaviors are both rated as “Often.”

Conversely, gambling, socializing with problematic peers, and sexual activity rank third, fourth, and fifth, which are risk behaviors that are both rated as “Sometimes” by the respondents. These are affirmed by the average weighted means of 3.42, 3.24, and 2.78, respectively. The least among the six risk behaviors is illegal drug use, which is rated “Seldom” by the respondents, with an average weighted mean of 1.63.

Certainly, in this instance, the results confirm that the adolescent children of the respondents demonstrated frequent involvement in smoking cigarettes and alcohol use. In other words, they observed their children smoking cigarettes and drinking alcoholic beverages, inside and outside their home. At times, they witnessed their children gambling, socializing with their problematic friends, and engaging in sexual activity with their opposite partners. However, they assessed their children to be rarely involved in using illegal drugs.

In a nutshell, the general average weighted mean of 3.17 divulged further that as a whole, the adolescent children of the parent-respondents are assessed to be “Sometimes” involved in the six (6) adolescent risk behaviors. These would also mean that they participated in occasional participation in these dangerous activities.

Hence, this result is exceedingly relevant on the standpoints of Defoe, I. N. et al., 2022, which highlighted that the most common reasons or motives by adolescents for engaging in risk behaviors like drinking large quantities of alcohol, smoking tobacco (cigarettes), and/or use of soft- drugs (cannabis), are for enjoyment, belonging, being cool/tough, having fun, experimenting and coping.

4. Testing Significant Relationship Between Parental Involvement (x1), Teaching Sex Education (x2), and Adolescent-Risk Behaviors (y)

To determine the relationship that exists between Parental Involvement (x1), Teaching Sex Education (x2), and Adolescent-Risk Behaviors (y), a one-to-one correspondence is done so that correlations between independent and dependent variables are ascertained. Table 4 shows the summary of values explaining the relationship between these variables.

In the course of correlational analysis and predictive ability, the relationship between these variables was tested for a significant relationship by the correlation method of analysis at the .05 level of significance.

Notably, the data verified that all the computed correlation coefficients between these variables ranged from $r=-0.407165$ to $r=-0.423061$, which are both indicative of marked and substantial relationships, all negative and therefore indicate indirect

relationships. These imply that “the higher the parental involvement there is, the lower the adolescent risk behaviors; and “the more sex education there is, the lesser the adolescent risk behaviors.”

On the other hand, when such relationships were tested for significance, the results showed that both parental involvement and sex education are found to be significant and strong predictors of adolescent risk behaviors. These are confirmed by the r-values of -0.407165 and -0.423061 with probability values (p-value of slope) of 0.024763 and 0.046219, which are both less than the 0.05 alpha level of significance (p-value \leq 0.05). Therefore, the null hypotheses are rejected, affirming that there are significant relationships between these variables.

Intuitively, these results divulge that parental involvement and the teaching of sex education among adolescents have a significant influence on the adolescent risk behaviors of their children. Further, these results disclose that parents should consistently act as good examples to their children and always provide direct communication, constantly remind their children of the religious beliefs that they have, and family customs should be maintained. Likewise, sex education is very important to be taught formally in school and informally at home.

The results of the study strongly uphold on the theories cited which are the Lifespan Wisdom Model (LSWM) by Romer, Reyna, & Satterthwaite (2017) and Developmental Neuro-Ecological Risk-taking Model (DNERM), by Defoe (2021) which both hypothesizing that physical risk exposure in itself predicts potentially maladaptive risk behavior such as substance dependence, unintended pregnancy and delinquency, attributable to curiosity and desire, need for exploration, high levels of impulsivity and weakness in cognitive control among adolescents.

Conclusions

In light of the above significant analysis and findings of the study, the following conclusions are now considered:

1. Although peers become an ever-increasing influence in the life of an adolescent, in the early years of junior & senior high school, the parents are still the primary role models, and they continue to have a strong indirect influence on their children throughout adolescence.
2. If all adolescent students have been exposed to similar information in the education process, and there continues to be a wide range of risk-taking behavior, then it is reasonable to assume that education alone is not the answer.
3. Students are important because they will serve as the future leaders of the country. As such, they need to be helped to ensure that they will be helping the nation in return.
4. Eventually, if the majority of the students were given utmost attention and guidance by the respective significant person in their lives, they would never come across severe adolescent risk behaviors.

5. An appropriate and relevant Sexuality Awareness and Risk Behaviors Intervention Program may reduce the incidence of unsafe sex, early teenage pregnancies, and other risk behaviors among adolescents in the community.

Recommendations

On account of the significant findings and conclusions of this study, the following are strongly recommended:

1. The adolescent students and their parents of the adopted community should be given free workshop seminars by the university on Sexuality Awareness education and Risk Behavior prevention.
2. A free Parental Involvement Seminar/Workshop should be provided to the parents to improve their knowledge in preventing adolescent risk behaviors, especially during the cognitive development years.
3. The university and the local government should consider embracing the importance of providing knowledge and consciousness on sexuality to young people and even to older people, to minimize the negative effects of this global phenomenon of adolescent pregnancies.
4. The local government should provide assistance and support for the sustainability of Sexuality Awareness education and Risk Behavior Intervention in different schools of Muntinlupa.
5. University managers may consider the proposed Sexuality Awareness and Risk Behavior Intervention Program and thereby review and reassess for further enhancement.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

Informed consent, obtained through a comprehensive and transparent process, was secured from all individual participants included in the study. This research strictly adheres to the principles of the Data Privacy Act of 2012. The authors affirm that they have no conflicts of interest to declare. All authors have thoroughly reviewed and unanimously agree with the contents of the manuscript, further ensuring the ethical conduct of this research.

Acknowledgments

Grateful acknowledgment is now extended to the researchers' family members, relatives, and friends. Above all, to the Holy Triune God: Father, Son, and Holy Spirit, and through the intercession of Mother Mary, for the energy, endurance, and guidance.

REFERENCES

- Adams-Wiggins, K. R. & El-Moslimany, H. 2021. Qualitative Inquiry in Early Childhood Education Research: Interviewing to Study Schools' Recognition of Funds of Knowledge in the Kindergarten Transition. Handbook of Research on Supporting Children's Well-

- Being During Early Childhood Transition to School, 17 (16): DOI: 10.4018/978-1-7998-4435-8.
- Bartolome, M.T. et al., 2017. Parental Involvement In The Philippines: A Review of the Literature. *International Journal of Early Childhood Education Care* Vol 6, 2017. ISSN 2289- 3156 /eISSN 2550-1763 (41-50).
- Berns et al. Adolescent Engagement in Dangerous Behaviors Is Associated with Increased White Matter Maturity of Frontal Cortex. *PLoS ONE*, 2009; 4 (8): e6773 DOI: 10.1371/journal.pone.0006773.
- Defoe, I. N. (2021). Towards a hybrid criminological and psychological model of risk behavior: the developmental neuro-ecological risk-taking model (DNERM). *Dev. Rev.* 62:100995. doi: 10.1016/j.dr.2021.100995
- Defoe, I. N. et al., 2022. Adolescents' own views on their risk behaviors, and the potential effects of being labeled as risk-takers: A commentary and review. Review article in *Frontier Psychology, Sec. Developmental Psychology, Volume 13 – 2022* | <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2022.945775>
- Hood, C. 2021. Kindergarten Writing: Utilizing Funds of Knowledge in a Digital Classroom. *Handbook of Research on Bridging Family-Teacher Relationships for ELL and Immigrant Students*, 14 (16): DOI: 10.4018/978-1-7998-4712-0.
- Kapetanovic, S., et al. (2019). Aspects of the parent–adolescent relationship and associations with adolescent risk behaviors over time. *Journal of Family Psychology*, 33(1), 1–11. <https://doi.org/10.1037/fam0000436>
- Kremelberg, D. *Introduction and Theoretical Background - Pearson's R, CHI-SQUARE, T-TEST, AND ANOVA*. Sage Publications Inc., 2009
- Lyu, K. et al., 2019. Parental Involvement Contributes to Family Cultural Capital in J District in Shanghai: Based on Taoyuan Private Primary Migrant School. *Handbook of Research on Social Inequality and Education*, 22 (25): DOI: 10.4018/978-1-5225-9108-5.
- Osturk, N. & Atsan, B. 2023. Parents' Perceptions of Foreign Language Assessment and Parental Involvement. *Handbook of Research on Perspectives in Foreign Language Assessment*, 22 (14): DOI: 10.4018/978-1-6684-5660-6.
- Tabor (2020). *Family ties: The Relation Between Siblings and Adolescent Risk-Taking Behavior*. master's thesis. Amsterdam: University of Amsterdam.
- The Borgen Project (2020). *Sex education in the Philippines*. <https://borgenproject.org>
- World Health Organization (WHO) 2019. *Adolescent Health*.